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Review Paper

An Overview of The Management of Life Style Disorders Through Ayurveda

Dr. Bhupendra Kumar*, **Dr. R. K. N. Priyangika**, **Amol Kadu**, **Dr. Dharti**, **Dr. Shubhangi Sharma**

Department of Agada Tantra, National Institute of Ayurveda (DU), Jaipur

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ABSTRACT

The incidence of lifestyle diseases like hypertension, diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia, and overweight/obesity associated with cardiovascular diseases is high on the rise. Cardio-vascular disorders continue to be the major cause of mortality representing about 30% of all deaths worldwide. The commonest causes of lifestyle disorders are eating unhealthy foods, over eating, over dependence on processed foods, energy drinks, artificial sweeteners and fast foods. According to Ayurveda, those diseases may be due to *pragyaparadha* (intellectual blemish) or *asatmya indyarthasamyoga* (unhealthy sensory perception), which results in disharmony in the body. Lifestyle diseases known internationally as ‘non-communicable diseases’ (NCD’s) or ‘chronic diseases of lifestyle’ (CDL) emerge from inappropriate relationship of people with their environment. Ayurveda has proven its role and importance in this area.

INTRODUCTION

Life style disorder termed as the “disease those are associated with once life style”. It is the habit of person that detracts him from healthy activities to sedentary routine which is the main cause of various health issues. Multi-dimensional diseases like the Lifestyle diseases and disorders are generally complex to cure; and the conventional medical system with its structural approach is still struggling to keep the check as one disease condition leads to another. Incidence of lifestyle diseases like Hypertension, Diabetes

Dyslipidemia, and overweight or obesity associated with Diseases is high on the rise. Cardio vascular disorders continue to be the major cause of mortality representing about 30% of all deaths worldwide¹. The commonest causes of lifestyle disorders are eating unhealthy foods, over eating, over dependence on processed foods, energy drinks, artificial sweeteners and fast foods. According to *Ayurveda*, those diseases may be due to *Pragyaparadha* (intellectual blemish) or *Asatmya Indyarthasamyoga* (unhealthy sensory perception), which results in disharmony

***Corresponding Author:** Dr. Bhupendra Kumar

Address: *Department of Agada Tantra, National Institute of Ayurveda (DU), Jaipur*

Email ✉: bkbhupendra190@gmail.com

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in the body. As Ayurveda is recognized as foremost life science and describes ways to prevent and manage lifestyle disorders; the world is being attracted towards its potential. Hence, Ayurveda able to provide better solution in the forms of proper dietary management, lifestyle advises, detoxification via *Panchakarma* and bio-purification procedures, medicaments, and rejuvenation therapies.

OBJECTIVES:

Ayurveda sets targets toward complete physical, psychological, and spiritual well-being of mankind and it makes this science a wonderful option in lifestyle disorder. On the basis of this scenario our study aimed,

1. To discuss the lifestyle disorders and causes via contemporary and Ayurveda perspective
2. To evaluate the important of regimens of *Dincharya* (daily regimen), *Ritu Charya* (seasonal regimen), *Panchakarma* (Detoxification and bio-purification) *Rasayanas* (Rejuvenation therapies) on management of life style disorders.
3. To find out the outcome of *Sadavritta* (ideal routine) and *Aacharya Rasayanas*(code of conduct) on management of life style disorders
4. To establish the action of *Ojas* (natural immunity) of individual health on management of lifestyle disorders
5. To introduce the practical approach to *Yoga* in current society.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A review of the literature was carried out using Google, Google Scholar, PubMed, and hand search. Here, the term hand search refers to searching the articles from cross-references of the articles selected for paper. Articles from 1990 to 2024, published in English, and 15 articles are finally included in this paper, which exclusively focus on management of life style disorders through ayurveda. Ayurvedic references are extracted from classical texts.

Understanding Life Style Disorders:

Lifestyle diseases can be defined as the diseases linked to the manner in which a person lives their life. These diseases are non-communicable. They arise from unhealthy habits and choices, including:

- **Poor Diet:** Diet is one of the modifiable behaviours that can help reduce cardio-metabolic risk and prevent chronic diseases, so an assessment of the general dietary intake of the population becomes essential². A poor diet often includes the consumption of processed foods, excessive sugars, unhealthy fats, and items with low nutritional value.
- **Poor Dietary Habits** - Some of the common poor dietary habits in Ayurveda include consuming incompatible food combinations (*Viruddha Ahara*), such as milk with fish or fruits with dairy, which can lead to toxin (*Ama*) formation and digestive disturbances. Overeating (*Adhyashana*) burdens the digestive system, while irregular eating habits (*Vishamashana*), such as skipping meals or eating at odd hours, disrupt the natural digestive cycle. Eating when the previous meal is not yet digested (*Ajirna Ahara*) can result in bloating and indigestion.
- **Sedentary lifestyle:** A sedentary lifestyle refers to a lack of significant physical activity. Sedentary behaviors have wide-ranging adverse impacts on the human body including increased all-cause mortality, cardiovascular disease mortality, cancer risk, and risks of metabolic disorders such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and dyslipidemia musculoskeletal disorders such as arthralgia and osteoporosis; depression; and, cognitive impairment.
- **Stress:** Any intrinsic or extrinsic stimulus that evokes a biological response is known as stress³. The activation of stress-related

neuroendocrine systems helps to maintain homeostasis, but excessive stress can damage body functions.

- **Lack of Sleep:** Sleep is a critical health behavior, important for all aspects of well-being⁴. A sleep disorder can affect your overall health, safety and quality of life. Poor sleep patterns can affect metabolic health and contribute to weight gain and stress-related disorders.
- **Substance Abuse:** Substance use disorder (SUD) is a persistent problem within society and an issue of increasing community awareness and concern. Smoking, excessive alcohol consumption, and drug use are major risk factors for many lifestyle-related diseases.

Life Style Disorders In Details:

A lifestyle disease is a disease linked to the way a person is living. Lifestyle diseases are associated to four modifiable lifestyle behaviors including smoking, unhealthy diet, physical inactivity and alcohol consumption that result in the development of non-communicable diseases (NCDs). Non-communicable diseases (NCDs), also known as chronic diseases, tend to be of long duration and are the result of a combination of genetic, physiological, behavioral, and environmental factors.⁵. Life style diseases includes:

- Diabetes
- Hypertension
- Cardio vascular diseases
- Behavioral problems
- Cancer
- Obesity etc.

Diabetes: Diabetes mellitus (DM), or simply diabetes, is a group of metabolic diseases in which a person has high blood sugar, either because the body does not produce enough insulin, or because cells do not respond to the insulin that is produced. This high blood sugar produces the classical symptoms of polyuria (frequent urination),

polydipsia (increased thirst) and polyphagia (increased hunger)⁶. The presence of DM shows increased risk of many complications such as cardiovascular diseases, peripheral vascular diseases, stroke, neuropathy, renal failure, retinopathy, blindness, amputations etc⁷. People with insulin-treated diabetes often struggle with weight gain, resulting in a vicious cycle of increasing insulin doses required to overcome the insulin resistance, leading to further weight gain, and ultimately resulting in higher cardiovascular risk⁸. In Ayurveda, Diabetes can be interpreted under the broad clinical entity described as *Prameha*. *Prameha* is classified on the basis of etiology; clinicopathology; body constitution and of prognosis. Causative factors which increase *medha* (fatty acid), *mutra*(urine) and *kapha* (body humour), generally leads to the pathogenesis of *Prameha*⁹.

Hypertension: Hypertension is the most common preventable risk factor for cardiovascular disease (CVD; including coronary heart disease, heart failure, stroke, myocardial infarction, atrial fibrillation and peripheral artery disease), chronic kidney disease (CKD) and cognitive impairment, and is the leading single contributor to all-cause death and disability worldwide¹⁰. Hypertension is a different kind of medical condition. In almost 90 % of patients it results from unknown factors (essential or primary hypertension) and only 10 % of patients have a specific cause of their hypertension (secondary hypertension). While essential hypertension cannot be cured, it can be controlled¹¹. According to Ayurvedic perspective, Hypertension is a symptom which is caused due to the *prasaravastha* followed by *sthanasamshraya* of vitiated *vata*dosha. Laziness, some diseases, improper lifestyle and food or sometimes unknown factors can vitiate *dosha* (morbid factor) and *dhatu*s which results in raised blood pressure which can lead the improper body functioning. Elevation in blood pressure is

also named as *uchharaktachaap* (tachycardia) in Ayurvedic Science¹².

Cardio vascular diseases: Cardio vascular diseases (CVD) is a collective term designating all types of affliction affecting the blood circulatory system, including the heart and vasculature, which, respectively, displaces and conveys the blood¹³. CVD is often driven by a combination of lifestyle factors, such as poor diet, physical inactivity, smoking, and excessive alcohol use, as well as underlying health conditions like high blood pressure, diabetes, and high cholesterol. While genetic predisposition also plays a role, most cardiovascular diseases are preventable through lifestyle modifications and medical management. From an Ayurvedic perspective, cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are understood through the balance of the body's three doshas: *Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha*. In Ayurveda, the heart is considered one of the most vital organs (*Hridaya*), and any imbalance in the *doshas* can disturb the proper functioning of the heart and circulatory system. *Hridroga*, the collective term for heart-related illnesses in Ayurveda, has become increasingly common as a result.

Behavioral problems: Lifestyle and behavioral factors strongly influence the odds of preventing or developing diseases and their complications. A person's overall lifestyle is the combination of individual behaviors which may be adverse, neutral, or beneficial to their health¹⁴. Adolescence is a period of several emotional, mental, and behavioral changes, and many adolescent problems are manifested in the form of emotional problems, conduct problems, hyperactivity, and peer-related problems¹⁵. Modern lifestyle choices, particularly those influenced by factors like technology, work pressure, diet, physical activity, and stress, can significantly impact mental and emotional well-being, leading to various behavioral shifts. Ayurveda is not only limited to body or physical symptoms but also give

comprehensive knowledge about spiritual, mental and social health. Ayurveda describes three *guna* of Mind and named as *Satwa* (Balance), *Raja* (Arrogance) and *Tama* (Indolence). When these *gunas* are in balance, they contribute to a healthy and harmonious mind. However, lifestyle factors such as poor diet, physical inactivity, smoking, and excessive alcohol use can disturb the balance of these *gunas*, leading to behavioral changes and mental imbalances.

Cancer: Cancer is a disease that begins with genetic and epigenetic alterations occurring in specific cells, some of which can spread and migrate to other tissues¹⁶. Cancer is often the result of mutations in the DNA of cells. These mutations can be caused by external factors such as smoking, radiation, viruses, and carcinogenic chemicals, or they can arise spontaneously due to errors during DNA replication.

Obesity: Obesity is a complex multifactorial disease that accumulated excess body fat leads to negative effects on health. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines overweight as BMI >25 kg/m² and obesity >30 kg/m² and describes these conditions as abnormal or excessive fat accumulation that is associated with increased health risk. Raised body mass index (BMI) is a risk factor for noncommunicable diseases such as diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and musculoskeletal disorders, resulting in dramatic decrease of life quality and expectancy¹⁷. *Charaka* describes obesity or *medoroga* or *sthaulya* as one of the eight types of non-desirable condition that plague the human body. It is a type of *Santarpanotha Vikar* caused by excessive nourishment. As per our review resulted several causes for lifestyle disorders that mentioned in Ayurveda. Any poison either *Sthavar* (inanimate), *Jangam* (animate) or *Kritim Visha* (artificial), which has not eliminated completely from the body or partially nullified after the using of anti-poisonous remedies, after

exposure to fire, the wind, the sun etc. and also the *Visha* devoid of ten qualities is called *Dushi Visha*. *Dooshivisha* is a type of "latent" or "slow poison." It refers to toxins that do not cause immediate harm but remain in the body for a long time. These toxins may come from various sources, such as improper digestion, poor dietary habits, environmental pollution, or unhealthy lifestyle choices. This gradual buildup of toxins weakens the immune system (*Ojas*) and disrupts cellular metabolism, potentially leading to chronic disorders including abnormal cell growth advance in cancer. *Garavisha* refers to "artificial or synthetic poison." It is a type of toxin that enters the body from external sources, such as exposure to chemicals, pesticides, drugs, or other unnatural substances. *Garavisha* is typically introduced into the body through environmental pollution, contaminated food, or harmful lifestyle choices. Continuous exposure to such toxins can damage the tissues (*Dhatus*), aggravate the doshas, and create imbalances that may lead to the development of Diabetes, hypertension Bronchial asthma or malignancies.

Ayurvedic Approach And Measures:

In the management of lifestyle diseases, Ayurveda offers various regimens including *Dinacharya* (daily regimen), *Ritucharya* (seasonal regimen), *Panchakarma* (five detoxification and bio-purification therapies), and *Rasayana* (rejuvenation) therapies. The *Sadvritta* (ideal routines) and *Aachara Rasayana* (code of conduct) are utmost important to maintain a healthy and happy psychological perspective.

Dinacharya (daily regimen): *Dinacharya* refers to ayurvedic daily routine recommendations that educate how to live a healthier, happier and longer life and avoid all diseases. Normal circadian rhythms are very important in day to day life to maintain biological clock¹⁸. Ayurveda suggests to begin daily habits with awareness, early rising, avoid suppression of natural urges and eliminate

wastes as per urge, keep the teeth & skin cleaned, regular use of massage (*Abhyanga*), regular daily bathing (bathing enhances the appetite and promotes longevity), consume suitable and wholesome diet according to the appetite and metabolic needs, since it is the basis of life and important for day-to-day promotion of health.

Ayurveda has also suggested avoiding late night sleep, eating stale foods, having sex with inappropriate partner & at unsuitable time and position and the misuse of senses. These might lead to imbalance in the circadian rhythms and thus long-term imbalance predisposes to lifestyle disorders. Therefore, one has to stay aware about this daily regimen for day-to-day promotion of health, boost immunity and prevention from lifestyle disorders¹⁹.

Ritucharya (seasonal regimen): Ayurveda has portrayed different rules and regimens (*Charya*), regarding diet and behavior to adapt seasonal variations easily without changing the body homeostasis²⁰. *Ritucharya* or a seasonal regimen is one of the best practices which are mentioned in classical text of Ayurveda, under this heading Ayurveda explains do's and don'ts in *Ahara* and *Vihara* through following this, one can stay healthy and live disease free life. As adaptations according to the changes, is the key for survival, the knowledge of *Ritucharya* (regimen for various seasons) is thus important. People do not know or ignore the suitable types of food stuffs, dressing, and others regimen to be followed in particular season, this leads to derangement of homeostasis and causes various diseases, such as obesity, diabetes, hypertension, cancer, and so on. Lifestyle diseases are a result of an inappropriate relationship of people with their environment. Onset of these lifestyle diseases is insidious, delayed development, and difficult to cure²¹. *Ritucharya* (Regimen to be followed according to season) is considered as one of the foundations for maintaining good health because it

maintains the climatic homology in form of *Dōṣa sām̐ya* (equilibrium) in different seasons.

Panchakarma: *Panchakarma* (biopurification) It is the only system of medicine in the world which proposes the need of regular purification of the human biological system from gross level to the molecular level to render it suitable for self-recovery and therapeutic responsiveness. These procedures are used in order to cleanse the body channels, to eliminate toxins out of the body, brings about the harmony of bio- humors (*Tridosha* i.e. *Vata*, *Pitta*, *Kapha*, and *Manasa Dosha* i.e. *Raja* and *Tama*) to obtain long-lasting beneficial effects which further leads to chemical balance inside the bio- system and thus provide the normal chemical and electrical environment in brain and ultimately restore the homeostasis.

Panchakarma is a collection of five active procedures of bio purification. These are 1. *Vaman* therapeutic emesis (mainly *kaphaj* disorders) 2. *Virechan*-therapeutic purgation (mainly *pittaj*) 3. *Aasthapan basti* therapeutic decoction enema (mainly *vataj* & *kaphaj* disorder) 4. *Anuvasan basti*-therapeutic oil enema(*vataj*) 5. *Nasya*-nasal medication (mainly *kaphaj* & *tridos*). When done properly, these promote psychosomatic health, rejuvenate the body and increase the receptivity and effectiveness of subsequent therapies. It also facilitates the absorption of nutrient and drugs administered thereafter in favor to attain their desired pharmacotherapeutic effects. *Panchakarma* also restore the mental health, reduces the stress and therefore, help in the prevention as well as management of many lifestyle disorders. *Panchakarma* is claimed for its preventive, promotive, prophylactic and rejuvenative properties²².

Rasayana (Rejuvenation): *Rasayan* therapy essentially refers to the process of tissue nourishment & rejuvenation. “*Labhodayo hi sastadinam rasadinam rasayanam*” *rasayana* has comprehensive scope to positive nutrition,

immunomodulator, free-radical scavenging, adaptogenic, anti-stress and nutritive effects, longevity & sustenance of mental & sensorial competence by promotion of mental & physical health also rejuvenation activity.

Rasayana is not only a drug therapy, but is a specialized procedure practiced in the form of rejuvenation recipes, dietary regimen and special health promoting right conduct and behavior, i.e. ‘*Acharya Rasayana*’. *Sushruta* (an ancient Ayurvedic surgeon) has narrated that *Rasayana* therapy arrests ageing (*Vayasthapam*), increase life span (*Ayushkaram*), intelligence (*Medha*) and strength (*Bala*) and thereby enable one to prevent disease. *Rasayana* enhances the functions of the whole body system. *Rasayana* becomes more fruitful and effective if it is preceded with suitable *panchakarma* (purificatory therapy).

Panchakarma is essentially a pretreatment equipping the body tissues for *Rasayana* therapy²³.

Acharya Rasayana: *Acharya Charaka* has said that one who speaks truth, who is free from anger, who abstains from alcohol and sexual activity, hurts no one (mentally, physically and even by action), avoids over strain, is tranquil of heart, fair-spoken, is devoted to repetition of holy chants and cleanliness, is endowed with understanding, diligent in spiritual endeavour, delights in reverencing the Gods, cows, brahmanas, teachers, seniors and elders, is attached to non-violence and is always compassionate, moderate and balanced in his walking and sleeping, spiritual in temperament and attached to elders and men who are believers and self-controlled and devoted to scriptural texts, should be considered as enjoying the benefits of vitalization therapy constantly.

The followers of these above-said *Sadvritta* (code of conduct) will reap all the benefits of *Rasayana* therapy. *Sadvritta* is not just a set of rules or guidelines. It is a way of living in harmony with nature’s rhythms. It is a path to optimal health and vitality. It covers all aspects of life, from the food

we eat to the thoughts we cultivate. It guides us on what to do and what to avoid²⁴.

FINDINGS:

The reviewed research highlights the effectiveness of behavioural modification that had mentioned in Ayurveda and interventions such as *Panchakarma*, *Dinacharya* (daily routines), *Ritucharya* (seasonal routines), and *Rasayana* (rejuvenation therapies). Holistic approaches that mentioned in Ayurveda can manage these lifestyle disorders by balancing and harmonizing the bodily *Dosha* status and mental status of the healthy individuals and Patients Further reviled undergoing Ayurvedic treatments showed improvements in overall metabolic health, reduced stress levels, and better physical activity. *Panchakarma* procedures like *Virechana* and *Vamana* provided detoxification benefits, promoting healthy body functioning and mental well-being. Mental stress and anxiotic life pattern are main causes that mentioned in the contemporary science and to overcome this condition implementing mental faculty like *Sadavritta* and *Achara Rasayana* principles enhanced the mental and spiritual well-being of patients. Publication emphasized that people who followed these guidelines showed better emotional stability and reduced stress and behavioural problems. All the time, in Ayurveda literature had given significant validation to wholesome foods and appropriate dietary pattern. *Hitha ahara* can provide enhance native immunity of the person and it leads to make the *Ojas* prominent condition in the body. In any and every condition then body will protect itself by producing natural component to combat the foreign materials. Therefore, on management of life style disorders individual immunity system is more crucial Practicable, simple *Yogasana* are already developed and practice in day- to -day life in globally. Therefore, there is high demand for Yoga and meditation in management of life style disorders.

DISCUSSION:

Ayurveda provides comprehensive care that improves not only physical health but also mental and emotional well-being. While modern medicine addresses lifestyle disorders with pharmacological interventions, Ayurveda focuses on prevention and root-cause resolution through natural means. This offers fewer side effects and long-term sustainability, especially in chronic conditions like diabetes and hypertension, where Ayurveda addresses lifestyle choices and mental health as contributing factors. The findings support Ayurveda's unique focus on treating the root causes of lifestyle disorders rather than just the symptoms. By integrating body, mind, and spirit. Ayurveda aimed prevention of diseases in healthy person and maintained its *Dosha* equilibrium. This balance is essential for maintaining health and preventing lifestyle disorders. Therefore, Ayurveda focuses on well balancing maintenance in body and mind. By enhancing the body's natural immunity (*Ojas*) through nutrition, herbs, and lifestyle modifications, making the body more resilient to diseases. Also Ayurvedic practices are appropriate alternative being it aims at restoring the balance between the body's three doshas (*Vata*, *Pitta*, *Kapha*) resulted in the stabilization of lifestyle disorders and improved health outcomes. Despite its efficacy, the modern adaptation of Ayurveda faces challenges, such as the general public's limited understanding of Ayurvedic practices. Integrating these ancient methods with contemporary health systems and increasing public awareness could enhance their effectiveness and acceptance

CONCLUSION:

This review study has enlightened the capacity of treating lifestyle disorders successfully via Ayurveda.

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